

12.26%); ν_{\max} (nujol) 3 220–3 150 (NH), 1 560, 1 530 (C=C, C=N) 1 460 (C–N) and 1 380 cm^{-1} (CH deformation in CH_2); δ (TFA) 2.18 (3H, s, CH_3), 3.82 (4H, 6- CH_2 and 7- CH_2) and 9.63 (s, NH). Similarly other compounds were prepared **7** (49%), ($n=2$, $R_1=\text{C}_6\text{H}_5$) m.p. 144°d (Found: S, 9.15. $\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{13}\text{N}_4\text{SBr}$ requires: S, 9.49%); **8** ($n=3$, $R_1=\text{H}$) (0.96 g, 35%), m.p. 220°d (Found: S, 11.42. $\text{C}_8\text{H}_{11}\text{N}_4\text{SBr}$ requires: S, 11.63%); ν_{\max} (nujol) 3 200, 1 620, 1 560, 1 520, 1 400, 1 360 and 1 200 cm^{-1} ; **9** ($n=4$, $R_1=\text{H}$) (0.9 g, 31%) m.p. 214° (Found: S, 10.81. $\text{C}_9\text{H}_{13}\text{N}_4\text{SBr}$ requires: S, 11.07%); ν_{\max} (KBr) 3 100, 1 585, 1 525, 1 400, 1 270 and 990 cm^{-1} ; **9** ($n=4$, $R_1=\text{C}_6\text{H}_5$) (1.64 g, 45%), m.p. 215 (Found: S, 8.29. $\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{17}\text{N}_4\text{SBr}$ requires: S, 8.76%).

3-Methylpyrazolo[3,4-d]thiazolo[3,2-a]benzimidazole (10; $R_1=\text{H}$): It was prepared by following the procedure as described in 6. The hydrobromide salt had m.p. 210°d. The free base was liberated with ammonia solution, (2.25 g, 73%) m.p. 240° (Found: C, 57.53; H, 3.42; S, 13.87. $\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_8\text{N}_4\text{S}$ requires: C, 57.89; H, 3.51; S, 14.03%); ν_{\max} (nujol) 3 070, 3 040, 1 600, 1 550, 1 450, 1 400, 1 270, 970, 895 and 790 cm^{-1} ; δ (TFA) 2.5 (3H, s, CH_3) and 7.55 (4H, s, ArH), NH remained unobserved. Similarly **11** ($R_1=\text{C}_6\text{H}_5$) was prepared (51%), m.p. 242° charred (Found: S, 8.07. $\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{18}\text{N}_4\text{SBr}$ requires: S, 8.31%).

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Qualitative Separation of Metal Ions by Thin Layer Partition Chromatography in Aqueous Glycolic Acid Media

L. DESHMUKH, P. D. KICHAMBARE
and
R. B. KHARAT*

Department of Chemistry, Institute of Science,
Nagpur-440 001

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EXTENSIVE studies have been carried out for the separation of cations using thin layers of silica gel G impregnated with *S*-butylamine, *t*-butylamine¹ and also with tri-*n*-octyl phosphine oxide, Alamine 336-S, Alamine 336-S oxide². The solutions of monobasic acids or their alkali metal salts are generally selected as the mobile phase. The literature study reveals the use of oxalic acid-oxalate³ and formic acid-formate⁴ in the solvent systems as mobile phases. Although glycolic acid forms stable complexes with many metal ions, its use in tlc has not been reported. This note describes a thin layer partition chromatographic method using aqueous solution of glycolic acid as an organic complexing agent and unimpregnated silica gel G as a solid support. The study aims to establish a simple, economical and time-saving method for the separation of metal ions from their ternary mixtures.

Experimental

All reagents used were of analytical reagent grade.

The stock solution (0.1 M) of Fe^{II} , Ni^{II} , Cu^{II} , Pb^{II} , Zn^{II} and Mn^{II} were prepared by dissolving their chlorides and sulphates and the solutions standardised⁵.

A slurry of silica gel G (E. Merck, Germany) in double-distilled water (1:3) was applied on glass plates (4×13 cm). Some plates were heated for 1 h at 110° and used for adsorption technique, while the others were dried overnight at room temperature and used for partition chromatography. The pH of glycolic acid solution of desired concentration was adjusted using sodium hydroxide and hydrochloric acid solutions. The metal ions or mixture of metal ions were spotted, dried and the plates were developed with aqueous glycolic acid. The solvent was allowed to run for 15 min by ascending technique and the metal ions were detected by spray reagents⁶. Mn^{II} was detected by 0.1% aqueous solution of 4-(2-pyridylazo)resorcinol and Cu^{II} by 3% aqueous potassium ferrocyanide. Mineral (1–2 g) were dissolved in 6N HCl. The insoluble

silicates were filtered off and filtrate was concentrated. These extracts were used for tlc. The R_f values of individual cations were calculated by the usual procedure.

Results and Discussion

Various experiments were carried out at room temperature to study the effect of pH, concentration of glycolic acid and development time for chromatoplates (Table 1) on the R_f values of individual cations. R_f value measurements were done in triplicate for each set of determination.

TABLE 1 - VARIATION OF R_f VALUES WITH DEVELOPMENT TIME

Time min	Glycolic acid = 0.05 M, pH = 2.5 Metal ions with R_f					
	Fe	Ni	Cu	Zn	Pb	Mn
5	0.40	0.60	0.44	0.41	0.41	0.59
10	0.31	0.66	0.42	0.44	0.40	0.66
15	0.33	0.73	0.46	0.48	0.46	0.63

Both thin layer adsorption and partition chromatography techniques were tried. However, in the present investigation, partition chromatography has been preferred over adsorption technique as the former requires less time for the development of chromatoplates. The variation in R_f values with pH at 0.1 M glycolic acid reveals that at pH 1 most of the cations move with the solvent front, while at pH 2.5 there is a considerable difference in the R_f values of various cations leading to good separation of metal ions. Therefore, pH 2.5 was fixed for all measurements.

It is observed that R_f values changes with the change in concentration of mobile phase. There is increase in R_f values of most of the cations with increase in concentration of glycolic acid solution. However, it has been found that there is significant difference in R_f values of cations at 0.05M concentration of mobile phase and good separations are possible at this concentration. Therefore, higher concentrations of glycolic acid were avoided and 0.05M concentration was fixed for further studies. The perusal of Table 1 reveals the effect of time on the R_f values of individual cations and it reveals that binary and ternary separations are possible in 5 and 10 min respectively. The method has been applied for the separations of ternary $Fe^{III}/Ni^{II}/M(II)$ and $Fe^{III}/Mn^{II}/M(II)$ (where M = Cu, Zn and Pb) in 10 min time.

The present method has also been employed for separation and detection of metal ions from the mineral samples from different mines of Udaipur district (Rajasthan). The results (Table 2) show excellent reproducibility, and the variation does not exceed 2% of average R_f values.

TABLE 2 - SEPARATION OF METAL IONS FROM MINERAL SAMPLES

Glycolic acid = 0.05 M, pH = 2.5, Time of development = 15 min

Samples no *	Metal ion %			R_f values		
	Fe	Pb	Mn	Fe	Pb	Mn
1	7.56	0.83	0.22	0.31	0.40	0.67
2	7.24	0.85	0.18	0.31	0.40	0.67
3	7.30	7.30	0.25	0.31	0.43	0.66

*From Baleria mines.

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Gold(III)-Gelatin Complex. A Specific Reagent for the Spectrophotometric Determination of Hydrazine and Formaldehyde in Water

TARASANKAR PAL* and PRADIP K. DAS

Department of Chemistry, Indian Institute of Technology, Kharagpur-721 302

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THE search for simple methods of determinations of both hydrazine and formaldehyde are of importance in analytical chemistry¹⁻³. There are a good number of methods^{2,4} for determining hydrazine and formaldehyde. In this communication a simple, non-toxic alkaline active reagent (reduction of Au^{III} -gelatin complex) for the direct spectrophotometric (at 540 nm) determinations of formaldehyde and hydrazine is proposed.